

Beyond Flat Repetitions: Uncovering Multi-instance and Nested Loops in Process Mining^{*}

Tina Yuting Huang^{1,*,\dagger}, Astria Hijriani^{2,\dagger}

¹*Cognizant Technology Solutions, Australia*

²*Department of Computer Science, University of Lampung, Indonesia*

Abstract

Despite the prevalence of complex loop structures in real-world processes, nested loops and their interaction with multi-instance loops remain underexplored. Existing process mining approaches lack clear definitions and frameworks for representing hierarchical loops, often leading to their misinterpretation as flat repetitions or structures that may actually represent multi-instance behavior. This obscures process logic, limits root-cause analysis, and reduces analytical value.

To address this gap, we propose a three-step methodology to construct enhanced event logs that explicitly capture hierarchical loop structures. This approach distinguishes nested loops from multi-instance behavior by leveraging recursive data relationships commonly found in enterprise systems. Grounded in industrial process mining experience, the framework improves transparency and supports a more accurate interpretation of complex process behavior. Through conceptual demonstration and experimental evaluation on engineered synthetic SAP data, we demonstrate how the approach reveals hidden loop structures and enhances interpretability. This work provides a research-in-progress foundation for structure-aware process mining and outlines directions for future automation, hybrid loop detection, and integration with object-centric process mining.

Keywords

Process Mining, Nested Loops, Multi Instance Loops, Event Log Quality, Loop Structure

1. Introduction

Process mining enables analysts to derive insights across the end-to-end process at various levels. However, one of the critical success factors for process mining projects is the quality of process models [1] or the quality of event logs. In real-world enterprise systems, processes are rarely linear, often involve nested subprocesses and complex loop behaviors. When nested subprocesses involve repetition or loops at different hierarchical levels, that substantially increases process complexity.

In case-centric event logs, such nested loops are represented as standard repetitions, depending on how a log is structured. Unlike standard loops (Figure 1a) that repeat within a single process level, nested loops (Figure 1c) span multiple hierarchical levels, where each

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^{*}Corresponding author.

^{\dagger}T.H. conceived the presented idea, developed the proposed framework, published a synthetic dataset, performed the evaluations, and completed the manuscript for the corresponding sections. A.H. made contributions to the sections of introduction, discussion, and future work. Both authors reviewed and finalized the final manuscript.

✉ tinahuang.qld@gmail.com (T. Y. Huang); astria.hijriani@fmipa.unila.ac.id (A. Hijriani)

🆔 0000-0002-0138-4961 (T. Y. Huang); 0000-0002-6073-6517 (A. Hijriani)

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Figure 1: Three types of loops and a hybrid pattern in hierarchical process trees.

sub-loop is dependent on its parent loop activity. This misrepresentation hinders root-cause traceability, obscures process transparency, and impairs effective process control, especially in cross-functional scenarios where events span modules or services managed by different organizational units. Errors within deeply nested sub-processes are challenging to diagnose due to multiple interdependencies, often leading to issues such as misaligned workflows or data discrepancies that cascade across process levels.

A clear understanding of hierarchical loop structures enables more accurate event log construction and significantly enhances process mining insights. While existing techniques such as loop unrolling [2, 3] and hierarchical discovery [4] enhance loop handling, the treatment of nested loops and their interactions with multi-instance loops remains underexplored. Current methods lack mechanisms to distinguish between standard, multi-instance, and nested loops, leading to ambiguity in trace interpretation and misalignment with actual business logic.

The study addresses how nested loops can be structurally distinguished from multi-instance loops in hierarchical process models and how event logs can be enhanced to visualize such hierarchical loop structures. This paper makes two contributions: (1) a conceptual framework for representing hierarchical loop structures in event logs and (2) a validated log transformation method demonstrating its utility on industry-grounded process models. The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews related work, Section 3 presents the proposed framework, Section 4 evaluates the framework, Section 5 provides a discussion, and Section 6 concludes the paper with directions to future work.

2. Background and Related Work

2.1. Loop Structure in Business Process

In Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN), loops represent repeated activities within a process [5]. BPMN distinguishes standard loops (Figure 1a) and multi-instance loops (Figure 1b) [6]. This paper extends this classification by introducing nested loops, where subprocesses are executed repeatedly within hierarchical parent-child relationships. To distinguish these structures, we introduce two operators: \parallel and \rightarrow .

- **Parallelism (\parallel):** $c_{i1} \parallel c_{j1}$ indicates that a process containing activity c which has variants i and j occurring simultaneously or sequentially at the same hierarchical level (Level 1).
- **Nesting (\rightarrow):** $c_{j1} \rightarrow c_{j2} \rightarrow c_{j3}$ indicates activity c in a process representing a vertical

descent and deeper hierarchical layers of the same process variant j , where c_{j2} is a child of c_{j1} , and c_{j3} is a grandchild.

2.2. Causes and Challenges of Nested Loops

Recursive Structure in Enterprise Systems. A recursive structure refers to a data structure that contains multiple hierarchical levels, each maintaining the same structure [7], allowing an element to refer to itself or to other elements within the structure [8]. Characterized by a fixed root and arbitrary nesting depths [8], this flexibility allows organizations to deploy arbitrary layers of sub-processes, thereby enhancing the modularity [9]. While such a self-referential, hierarchical dependencies enhances the structural flexibility to model complex business logic, it introduces significant challenges for process discovery and control. Specifically, the absence of clearly identifiable root elements makes it difficult to track issues and identify root causes across homogeneous hierarchical structures. When operational discrepancies or data anomalies occur within nested layers, such structural ambiguity obscures the execution path, impeding root-cause traceability and undermining effective process governance.

At the relational data level, such a recursive structure is characterized by three core columns: the object identity (primary key), the upper-level object (foreign key), and the direct parent object via a self-referential association or upper level object. Systematically decoding an object's recursive, parent-child, and self-referential relationships serves as the foundation for enabling loop unrolling and restoring process transparency.

System Functional and Process Segregation. Beyond recursive, self-referential structural complexity, cross-functional business silos further compound operational challenges. In an organizational context, silos refer to barriers that restrict communication and effective collaboration across teams, limiting end-to-end visibility and efficiency [10]. In enterprise systems like SAP, Oracle, and ServiceNow, system silos stem from module designs for managing complex intra-organizational operations. While these platforms integrate core functions (e.g. supply chain, finance, and customer relations), their modular architecture often leads to functional segregation, where each module operates within its own system boundaries, creating information and decision-making silos [11]. Moreover, these modules are typically managed by a separate team, reinforcing business unit and process silos.

2.3. Handling Complex and Dynamic Loops in Process Mining

Previous work has proposed techniques such as loop unrolling [2] and pattern-based preprocessing [12] to handle complex loop behaviors. However, these approaches lack clear definitions of nested loops and do not distinguish them from hybrid forms of multi-instance loops. Context-based label splitting [13] improves model precision but does not capture hierarchical loop structures. Without sufficient data context, complex loops may be interpreted as standard, multi-instance, or hierarchical, despite representing fundamentally different execution logic and business implications.

Traditional flat event logs usually produce highly complex and confusing process models. To solve this, some studies emphasize the need to break processes down into clear hierarchical levels [14]. Having this clear hierarchy is also crucial to find exactly where a process fails. Recent

analysis uses Shapley values to pinpoint how specific structural components in a workflow contribute to the violation of logical constraints [15]. However, precise diagnostic tracking is unachievable if the process model aggregates distinct behavioral iterations into a single unconstrained loop structure.

3. Proposed Framework

3.1. Preliminaries

This section introduces the following definitions for context-enhanced structural event data used in the three-step transformation framework proposed in this paper.

Event Log, Trace and Event Attribute. An event log L is a collection of traces. A trace is a finite sequence of events $\sigma = \langle e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n \rangle$, where each event e is a collection of attributes. Let U_e be the universe of events. Every event $e \in U_e$ is mapped to its corresponding attributes:

- $\#_{act}(e) \in U_a$: activity of event e .
- $\#_{trans}(e) \in U_{trans}$: the transaction type(s) of event e .

Loop Activity and Loop Attribute. Let $LP \in U_a$ be a loop activity in trace σ . An activity is considered a loop if it occurs at least twice within a process execution:

$$IsLoop(LP, \sigma) \Leftrightarrow \exists i < j : \#_{act}(e_i) = \#_{act}(e_j) = LP.$$

Let $U_{LD} \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ be the universe of loop depths and $U_{RL} = \{1, \perp\}$ the universe of root-loop identifiers. Two structural attributes are used to capture the hierarchical complexity of any identified loop activity LP :

- $\#_{depth}(LP) \in U_{LD}$: Nesting depth of a loop activity.
- $\#_{rootlevel}(LP) \in U_{RL} \cup \{\perp\}$: Root-level loop identifier.

Figure 2: Recursive Data Structure for Identifying Nested and Multi-Instance Loops.

3.2. Discovery of Multi-instance and Nested Loops

As aforementioned, hierarchical dependencies and nested loops stem from the recursive data structure within enterprise systems, where decoding the three core columns (object identity, upper-level object, and direct parent) provides the critical structural data to detect multi-instance behaviors and map nested loop structures. Figure 2 illustrates the application of the three core

columns in discovering the hierarchical relationship between *Cr/Dr Request* and *Invoice* in *VBAK* table, where providing traceability by linking credit requests to original invoices, while the recursive structure between *Cr/Dr Request* and *Parent* enables the identification of nested hierarchies within those requests.

To apply data-driven automatic detection of such loop types, we propose a three-step method to systematically detect and analyze complex loop behaviors that often remain obscured in traditional case-centric process mining models.

Step 1 - Hierarchical Loop Level Annotation. This step aims to identify and annotate loop activities with their hierarchical depth. For each loop activity LP , if it is a first-level loop, set $\#_{\text{depth}}(LP_{\text{first}}) = 1$; for nested loops, recursively assign depth by incrementing the parent's depth by 1:

$$\#_{\text{depth}}(e) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \#_{\text{act}}(e) = LP \text{ and } \#_{\text{rootlevel}}(LP) = 1, \\ \#_{\text{depth}}(LP_{\text{first}}) + 1 & \text{if } \#_{\text{depth}}(LP) \neq 1 \\ \perp & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Step 2 - Label Splitting for Multi-Instance Loops. For first-level loops where $\#_{\text{depth}}(LP) = 1$, transform event log $L \rightarrow L'_1$ using $LP \rightarrow LP \oplus \#_{\text{trans}}(e)$ to split multi-instance loops:

$$\#'_{\text{act}}(e) = \begin{cases} \#_{\text{act}}(e) \oplus \#_{\text{trans}}(LP) & \text{if } \#_{\text{depth}}(LP) = 1 \text{ or } \#_{\text{rootlevel}}(LP) = 1, \\ \#_{\text{act}}(e) & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Step 3 - Unrolling Nested Loops. For nested loops where $\#_{\text{depth}}(LP) > 1$, transform the enhanced event log $L'_1 \rightarrow L'_2$ by using $LP \rightarrow LP \oplus \#_{\text{depth}}(LP)$:

$$\#'_{\text{act}}(e) = \begin{cases} \#_{\text{act}}(e) \oplus \#_{\text{depth}}(LP) & \text{if } \#_{\text{depth}}(LP) > 1 \\ \#_{\text{act}}(e) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The following algorithm *HybridLoopTransform(L)* integrates the proposed framework to address the challenge of identifying complex loop structures within an event log L .

Algorithm 1: HybridLoopTransform(L)

```

1 # Step 1: Hierarchical Loop-Level Annotation.
2 for each trace  $\sigma$  in event log  $L$ 
3   for each identified loop activities  $LP$  in  $\sigma$ 
4     if  $\#_{\text{act}}(e) = LP$  and  $\#_{\text{rootlevel}}(LP) == 1$ , then set  $\#_{\text{depth}}(e) \leftarrow 1$  ▷ annotate as a first-level loops
5     else if  $\#_{\text{act}}(e) = LP$  and  $\#_{\text{rootlevel}}(LP) > 1$  do
6        $\#_{\text{depth}}(e) \leftarrow$  current depth + 1 ▷ annotate with nested loop depth
7   output: Event log annotated with 'Loop Level' to indicate root-level loops and loop depth

8 # Step 2: Label splitting for outer loops (loop depth = 1)
9 for each  $e$ , if  $\#_{\text{act}}(e) == LP$  and  $\#_{\text{depth}}(e) == 1$ , then
10   set  $\#'_{\text{act}}(e) \leftarrow LP \oplus \#_{\text{trans}}(LP)$  ▷ split label for multi-instance loops
11 output: Transformed event log  $L'_1$  with updated multi-instance loops

12 # Step 3: Unrolling nested loop (loop depth > 1)
13 for each  $e$ , if  $\#_{\text{act}}(e) == LP$  and  $\#_{\text{depth}}(e) > 1$ , then
14   set  $\#'_{\text{act}}(e) \leftarrow LP \oplus \#_{\text{depth}}(LP)$  ▷ encode nested loop level in activity name
15 output: transformed event log  $L'_2$  supporting nested loop differentiation

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The proposed framework acts as a preprocessing layer that transforms event logs into structure-aware representations, enabling more accurate downstream process mining analysis.

4. Evaluation

To evaluate the efficacy of the proposed transformation method, we engineered a synthetic dataset from scratch comprising a recursive SAP *VBAK* structure and corresponding invoice-credit memo event logs [16]. This dataset was specifically designed to simulate complex recursive process loops, real-world business constraints, and process loop anomalies, establishing a controlled, deterministic ground-truth environment. Based on this synthetic dataset, we conducted an experimental evaluation and a deterministic validation driven by the semantic constraints of the enterprise schema. Rather than relying on traditional conformance checking, which evaluates horizontal behavioral fitness but is blind to vertical hierarchy, our evaluation focus on assessing whether the discovered process model accurately reflects the structural integrity and cardinality correctness determined by the underlying recursive database structure.

4.1. Conceptual Demonstration

We provide a conceptual validation to illustrate how the framework utilizes recursive data to identify multi-instance and nested loops.

$$\begin{aligned}
 L &= [\langle a, b, c \rangle^{40}, \langle a, b, c^4 \rangle^{10}, \dots] \\
 L'_1 &= [\langle a, b, c_i \rangle^{30}, \langle a, b, c_j \rangle^{10}, \langle a, b, c_i, c_j^3 \rangle^{10}, \dots] \\
 L'_2 &= [\langle a, b, c_i \rangle^{30}, \langle a, b, c_j \rangle^{10}, \langle a, b, c_i, c_{j1}, c_{j2}, c_{j3} \rangle^{10}, \dots]
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 3: Unrolling Multi-instance and Nested Loops

Figure 3 illustrates the transformation of an initial event log L into L'_1 (multi-instance parallelism identification) and L'_2 (hierarchical nesting identification). Event log L containing a standard trace $\langle a, b, c^4 \rangle$, which maps to a common SAP Order-to-Cash workflow: Invoice(a)→ Delivery(b)→ Credit Request (c) where c^4 represents multiple iterations of activity c . This flat presentation is structurally ambiguous. This trace is aligned with the recursive data example illustrated in Figure 2, where the loop in activity c containing two variants $\{i, j\}$. The hidden relationship within c^4 can be denoted as $\{c_{i1} \parallel c_{j1} \rightarrow c_{j2} \rightarrow c_{j3}\}$. By identifying these multi-instance and nested repetitions, the trace transformation is as follows:

$$\sigma_i = \langle a, b, c_i, c_j^3 \rangle \implies \langle a, b, c_i, c_{j1}, c_{j2}, c_{j3} \rangle \implies \langle a, b, c_{i1}, c_{j1}, c_{j2}, c_{j3} \rangle$$

The semantic approach displayed in Figure 3 demonstrates that leveraging the logic residing in the enterprise data tables (see Figure 2) enables the accurate separation of multi-instance and hierarchical nesting.

4.2. Experimental Data and Transformation

Ground Truth Dataset. The synthetic data table *VBAK* defines the true hierarchical recursive relationships between invoices and credit requests. By analyzing the *Cr/Dr Request* and *Parent*

columns, the structural distribution of Credit Request objects is revealed, explicitly differentiating between invoice-linked requests and nested credit-to-credit requests relationships:

- Total Invoices (123): directly link to 133 Credit/Debit Request (root-level).
- Total Requests (232): 133 root level requests with 99 nested requests distributed across levels 2 through 6 (57→17→15→5→5).

Annotation and Transformation. To optimize visualization (Log original→Log L), credit and debit requests were relabeled under a unified name (Cr/Dr), as they represent the same document type with opposite value signs. Downstream non-critical activities (such as *Credit Memo* and *Debit Memo*) were excluded for clarity. We applied the proposed three-step transformation method to generate enhanced event logs ($L \rightarrow L_1 \rightarrow L_2$) shown in Figure 4.

4.3. Experimental Evaluation

Figure 4: Three process model comparison

Correcting Cardinality Distortion. In the standard flat Log (L), the relationship between invoices and Credit Requests as a simple 1:n behavioral loop. This representation creates a cardinality fallacy, treating 232 requests as direct descendants of 123 invoices. By contrast, the transformed model (L_2) correctly attributes the 133 requests to their multi-instance origins from the 99 nested chains, completely restoring true object cardinality and aligning the process model with the underlying database fabric.

Table 1

Log Transformation Metrics and Interpretability Comparison

Event Log	Trace/Event/Activity	Cardinality (Invoice:Request)	Interpretability
L	123 / 538 / 4	123:232	Low
L'_1	123 / 538 / 8	123:(133→99)	Medium (Nesting Packed)
L'_2	123 / 538 / 12	123:(133 → (57→17→15→5→5))	High (Fully Unrolled)

Process Transparency and Interpretability. The transformed Logs L'_1 and L'_2 reveal the true process fabric by distinguishing between distinct types of object creation obscured in Log L .

- Directly-only variants: The discovered models for L'_1 and L'_2 in Figure 4 show the four types of root-level *Create Cr/Dr* explicitly: *Relationship*, *Returns*, *Invoice Correction* and *General Credit Request*. Activities such as *Create Cr/Dr-Relationship* or *Create Cr/Dr-Inv Corre* occurs as independent instances and rarely trigger nested chains.
- Cascading variants: The *Create Cr/Dr>Returns* variant shows a unique pattern of deep-nested chains. The transformation unrolls the 99 indirect requests into specific hierarchical levels (57→17→15→5→5).

Noise Filtering and Hierarchical Abstraction. To distill the structural core of the transformed L'_2 , intermediate operational activities are filtered out, leaving only the object creation milestones: A (*Create Invoice*) and C (*Create Cr/Dr Request*). Figure 5 illustrates this core process, enabling the direct observation of hierarchical structures and cardinality relationships. Through grouping or expanding the Root Level ($C_{i1}, C_{j1}, C_{p1}, C_{q1}$) or Nested Level elements of activity ($C_{j2}, C_{j3}, C_{j4}, \dots$) accordingly, this approach further provides the flexibility to explore either level for more detailed investigation.

Figure 5: Noise Filtering and Flexible Exploration of Root-level or Nested Loops

5. Discussion

This study addresses a critical gap in loop structure theory by establishing a robust methodology for modeling and interpreting dynamic, hidden loop behaviors. While existing work primarily defines basic loop types in BPMN [5, 6], our approach differentiates standard, multi-instance, and nested loops based on hierarchical data relationships, addressing a gap in both process modeling and event log semantics. Furthermore, we build on preprocessing techniques such as loop unrolling [2] and context-based label splitting [13] by introducing depth-aware hierarchical annotations for structural disambiguation of nested structures, an area previously underexplored.

Practically, the method significantly improves transparency and control in complex business workflows (e.g. credit management) by uncovering hidden dependencies masked by loop aggregation. Its application in an external audit demonstrates concrete value for root-cause identification, process compliance, and internal control. By explicitly encoding loop origin and nesting depth, our methodology establishes cross-module traceability across diverse enterprise ecosystems, including *SAP SD/CRM/FI* and *ServiceNow Sales Order/Work Order/Project* modules.

This study has several limitations. First, the framework relies on a targeted configuration tailored to domain-specific data schemas (e.g., *SAP VBAK*), which may require adaptation to achieve automated scalability across diverse systems. Second, the experimental evaluation applies a single dataset, so broader applicability should be tested in diverse contexts and data environments. Third, the current deterministic framework assumes the pattern and structure observed in the *SAP* credit memo operations, which require optimization when handling more complex hybrid patterns.

6. Conclusion and Future Work

By providing explicit semantic tracking of nesting depths and loop origins, the proposed framework resolves structural ambiguities that traditional preprocessing techniques overlook, ultimately improving downstream process transparency and root-cause analysis.

Future work will focus on four key areas: automating the discovery process by developing detection algorithms for hybrid loop patterns, extending the framework to object-centric process mining (OCPM) to capture multi-entity interactions, integrating the resulting structure-aware event logs with Agentic-AI techniques for autonomous diagnostics, and conducting broader experimental evaluations on datasets from diverse domains to validate scalability.

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Declaration on Generative AI

During the preparation of this work, the authors utilized Gemini to verify grammar, spelling, and mathematical formulas. Additionally, T.H. used the tool to scale the manually designed synthetic dataset by generating an equivalent volume of data adhering to the baseline patterns. Following generation, T.H. manually refined the dataset, cross-checked the underlying data logic against the enterprise schema constraints, and reviewed the final output. The authors maintain full accountability for the integrity and content of this publication.

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